

Project ID: Fly-Radar

Project Title: “Low-frequency multi-mode (SAR and penetrating) radar onboard light-weight UAV for Earth and Planetary exploration”

Call: H2020-MSCA-RISE-2020

WP8: Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

D8.1: WEBSITE FRAMEWORK AND SOCIAL TOOLS

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1. Fly-Radar Website Framework and Social Tools

1.1 Project Website

The project website is available at:

→ <https://www.flyradarproject.eu/>

Figure 1: Website Home Page

The active domain flyradarproject.eu is registered with the Italian provider Aruba.

For the project, the Premium Managed WordPress Hosting has been chosen, which includes:

- Domain registration
- Unlimited email accounts
- 10 GigaMail
- 5 PEC accounts on domain
- Unlimited web space and traffic and
- Support on recommended plugins

The service is hosted in a remote server based on GNU/Linux, with 24/7 technical assistance, malware detection and daily backups.

For security reasons, the Domain Validation SSL Certificate will be renewed automatically every year.

The homepage is characterised by: a header, different sections and a footer.

The **header** is made up of the Fly-Radar logo on the left, the menu in the middle and the European logo on the right.

The menu is divided as follow:

- About us
- The project
 - × Project Objectives
 - × Project Background
 - × Project Status
 - × Project Deliverables
 - × Results
- Partners
- Dissemination
 - × Publications
 - × Conferences
 - × Workshop

- ✘ Meetings
- ➔ Videos
- ➔ Software
- ➔ Cloud

In the first section, there is the Fly-Radar Logo and the title of the project with a video in the background, along with information on the consortium.

The second section describes the project in terms of main project objectives, provides an overview of the project background, with click buttons that refer to “project Objectives”, “Project Background”, etc., and will include the project deliverables, results and status.

The third section is divided in two parts: meeting and events; which will be continuously updated as the project progresses.

Subsequently, the fourth part is dedicated to communication and dissemination activities.

In the fifth part all the project videos, including for training activities, will be made available.

Open source software will be stored in the software section of the website (sixth section).

Finally, the project cloud is accessible from the cloud section (seventh section).

The footer is divided in two parts:

- ➔ At the bottom, with black background, there are the information related to the EU funding “*This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under MSCA-RISE2020 grant agreement No 101007973*”, along with the EU logo, and to Copyright.
- ➔ The upper part is divided into three columns:
 - ✘ In the first one, below the Fly-Radar logo, it is possible to click on the social icons and access them;
 - ✘ In the second one, there are links to access the project office contact details and the privacy and cookies policy;
 - ✘ In the third one, there is a module to subscribe to the newsletters.

1.2 Social Media

Access to project social media (Twitter and Facebook) is provided at the bottom of each of the website pages by simply clicking on the twitter and facebook logos beneath the Fly-Radar logo. Additionally, in the home page, there is a dedicated section “Follow us on Twitter and Facebook”. The Twitter Profile @FlyRadar1 and the Facebook Profile @flyradarproject have been created in May 2021, and are currently available.

Figure 2: Access to Social Media

... FOLLOW US ON TWITTER AND FACEBOOK ...

The screenshot displays a collection of social media posts. On the left, three tweets from FlyRadar are shown, dated from 2 to 3 months ago. The first tweet is a retweet of @Micascisto celebrating a milestone in Mars coverage. The second is a retweet of @NASASolarSystem regarding the Juno mission's flyby of Ganymede. The third highlights an experimental radar package for space and terrestrial technology. On the right, three Facebook posts are visible, dated from August 2021. The first is an Italian-language post about an updated image. The second is an English post from JPL NASA.gov titled 'Clays, Not Water, Are Likely Source of Mars 'Lakes'', discussing recent studies on subsurface lakes. The third is an English post about a new radar interpretation for thick ice.

Figure 3: Fly-Radar Twitter Page

Figure 4: Fly-Radar Facebook Page

END OF DELIVERABLE

